

THE EFFECT OF INTERFACIAL STRENGTH, MICROSTRUCTURE AND MOISTURE ON TRANSVERSE CRACKING IN COMPOSITES

Walter L. Bradley, Catherine Wood and Candy Chatawanich
Center for Mechanics of Composites and Department of Mechanical Engineering, Texas A&M
University, College Station, TX 77843, USA

ABSTRACT

The development of transverse cracks in polymeric composites with multi-axial layups has been observed directly by loading specimens in an environmental scanning electron microscope. Graphite/epoxy composite specimens nominally dry and after soaking in seawater have been studied as have been dry E-glass/epoxy composites. The failure scenario begins with interfacial failure at local homogeneities, such as resin rich regions or voids, at laminate stresses much lower than that required for this local damage to coalesce and grow into a transverse crack, resulting in propagation rather than initiation controlled fracture.

INTRODUCTION

Transverse cracking is usually the first damage which develops in laminates with off-axis plies. A recent review article summarizes the considerable progress made in analyzing transverse cracking in polymeric composite materials.¹ A recent three-dimensional finite element analysis has shown that the energy release rate for growth of transverse microcracks is virtually independent of the length of the propagating crack.² This surprising outcome explains the success of various approaches in the literature^{1,3} which assume that the incremental energy release rate for a growing transverse microcrack equals the average energy release rate for the complete transverse crack, an assumption which is not altogether intuitive.

If the energy release rate is essentially constant as a microcrack grows across a ply to become a complete, transverse crack, one might expect transverse cracking to be initiation controlled. At least four recent studies⁴⁻⁷ implicitly make this very reasonable assumption that interfacial debonding leads immediately to transverse cracking, in principle allowing the calculation of the interfacial strength from the laminate stress at which transverse cracking appears. However, none of the above mentioned studies has provided any direct evidence that initiation of ply microcracking leads immediately to transverse cracking. Furthermore, none of the above mentioned models take any note of microstructural features such as voids or resin rich regions, which might play a significant role in the ply stress at which interfacial failure begins.

The recent interest in the use of composite materials in marine environments gives impetus to also better understand the effect of moisture on both initiation of microcracks and their subsequent propagation. Moisture can affect the interfacial strength in two ways, by reducing

the chemical adhesion at the fiber/matrix interface and by relaxing the residual compressive stresses in the radial direction at the fiber matrix interface.

The purpose of this study has been to observe the initiation and propagation of microcracking in multi-axial, polymeric composite laminates with polished edges as they are loaded in-situ in an environmental scanning electron microscope.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

A tensile specimen is used which has a region of the gage section with arched edges, as seen in Figure 1, produced by careful grinding and polishing to reveal fibers and matrix clearly using a specially developed technique. The purpose of this specimen geometry is to localize the region where damage is initiated to increase the possibility of seeing initiation of damage. Two polymeric composite systems have been studied: (1) TACTIX 556 (Dow Chemical) with IM-7 fibers with a (+45/0/-45/90)_s stacking sequence made from prepreg and (2) DGEBA crosslinked with mPDA, reinforced with E-glass fibers 158B (Owens Corning), which has an epoxy compatible sizing, with a (+-45/90)_s stacking sequence. The polishing is accomplished by attaching grinding and polishing materials to metal doweling which is rotated using a drill. This polishing tool used in combination with templates allows the specimen to be prepared with a gradually varying gage width along the length of the gage section.

The specimens are subsequently tested in an ElectroScan environmental scanning electron microscope which obviates the need for coating the specimens to avoid charging. Testing is conducted using a mechanical stage manufactured by Ernest Fullham, Inc (4500N capacity) with a mechanical drive and a load cell, with testing conducted in displacement control. The load is applied incrementally with the specimens carefully examined at each load level to determine whether local interfacial failure, local microcracking or transverse cracking has occurred in the 90° plies. Damage is monitored until a load is reached at which transverse cracks are present in the 90° plies.

Some of the TACTIX 556/IM-7 composite specimens were soaked (aged) in simulated seawater, produced by mixing distilled water and "Instant Ocean", a mix of salt and trace elements that can be purchased at pet stores to provide a simulated ocean environment for tropical fish. The specimens were weighed periodically and it was determined that the eight-ply laminate reached its saturation level of moisture absorption in approximately four months. However, the specimens were maintained in the simulated seawater for an additional five months, for a total of nine months prior to testing.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The first indication of damage in the unaged, TACTIX 556/IM-7, hereafter referred to as graphite/epoxy, is interfacial debonding adjacent to a resin rich region, as seen in Figure 2 at a laminate stress of 145 MPa (loaded approximately vertically in this photograph). At 207 MPa of laminate stress, the local debonds coalesce to give a small microcrack. With the exception of three local debonds seen nearby in a region of high fiber density, no other indications of damage were noted. Further increases in stress in 14 MPa increments did not produce any additional growth of this microcrack adjacent to the resin rich region into the high fiber density portions of the microstructure until a laminate stress of 352 MPa was reached, as seen in Figure 3. A similar microcrack bordering an adjacent resin rich region is also seen in Figure 3. At 359 MPa of laminate stress, these cracks begin to coalesce, which they do at 355 MPa, as seen in Figure 4.

By contrast, initial debonding leading to transverse cracking for the aged graphite/epoxy composite occurs all at once at 179 MPa, as seen in Figure 5, suggesting initiation controlled fracture rather than propagation controlled fracture, as was seen for the unaged specimen in Figures 2-4. It is not clear whether this difference is due to the absorbed moisture, which was 1.2% of the weight of the matrix, or to the difference in microstructure (no resin rich regions in the aged specimen), even though both specimens were cut from the same laminate.

The DEGBA/mPDA reinforced with 158B E-glass fibers, hereafter referred to as the glass/epoxy composite, was tested only in the unaged condition (no seawater soaking). The results are presented in Figures 6-8. The local microcrack between two resin rich regions seen in Figure 6 was first observed as two debonds at a laminate stress of 8.17 MPa, with local coalesces of these debonds into a microcrack occurring at 32.7 MPa of laminate stress. At a nearby location, debonding is just beginning on two adjacent sides of a void at 28.9 MPa of laminate load, Figure 7. However, growth of this damage is quite slow until a laminate load of 60.3 MPa is reached, Figure 8. Again, the transverse cracking is seen to be propagation rather than initiation controlled.

DISCUSSION

The most surprising outcome of this investigation has been the observation that failure may occur by premature damage development at local inhomogeneities in the microstructure. Most models in the literature do not consider the microstructure; yet the microstructure appears to be potentially very important unless processing can be done that avoids both void formation and resin rich regions. Particularly for filament wound parts, inhomogeneities are likely to be the rule rather than the exception.

One would intuitively expect the fibers bordering a resin rich region to be less highly stressed due to laminate loading, since the resin rich regions will act like soft elements. However, if one considers the residual stresses due to thermal contraction on cooldown, debonding adjacent to a resin rich region makes more sense. For a homogeneous distribution of fibers, the resin contracts more than the fibers on cooldown, leaving the fiber/matrix interface in residual compressive stresses in the radial direction. However, adjacent to a resin rich region, the pure resin will have a much greater thermal contraction than the bordering fiber matrix region, giving residual tensile stresses at the boundary, the resin rich region being analogous to a trampoline. A more detailed analysis of this phenomena has been presented elsewhere⁸.

The effect of moisture, in so far as it affects residual stresses, will depend on the microstructure. For a homogeneous distribution of fibers, the residual compressive stresses in the radial direction will be relaxed by the swelling that the absorbed moisture produces, making debonding easier. On the other hand, the residual tension at the border of a resin rich region will be relaxed, making the initiation of fiber debonding more difficult. The moisture could also degrade the interfacial adhesion. Thus, it is not surprising that the effect of moisture on transverse tensile strength reported in the literature has been quite varied.

It is clear that understanding transverse cracking and transverse tensile strength for both dry and moisture saturated specimens should give due consideration to the microstructure if meaningful results are to be obtained.

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Figure 1. Tensile specimen.

Figure 2. First indication of interfacial failure is in fibers that border resin rich region of graphite/epoxy composite microstructure.

Figure 3. Microcrack growth from border of resin rich region in Figure 2 and adjacent resin rich region.

Figure 4. Coalescence of microcracks from Figure 3 into a transverse crack in graphite/epoxy.

Figure 5. Transverse crack which formed all at once in seawater saturated graphite/epoxy.

Figure 6. Microcracking in region between two resin rich regions in an E-glass/epoxy composite.

Figure 7. Two local debonds adjacent to a void near the microcrack seen in Figure 6.

Figure 8. Coalescence of debond initiated microcracks seen in Figures 6 and 7.